

THE EFFECTS OF FOOTBALL COACHES' STAI ANXIETY LEVEL ON PROBLEM SOLVING SKILL

Katra Hasimⁱ,

Adilogullari Ilhan

Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University,
Turkey

Abstract:

This study aim of the examination relationship between anxiety and problem solving skills who participated to the study coaches of the football. 95 volunteers football coach participated to the study where were Bursa and Canakkale provinence. To obtain trait anxiety state data of tranis the 20-item developed by Beck Traiy Anxiety State Inventory(TASI) were used. Problem Solving Skills (PSS) data, developed by Heppner and Petersen (1982) and to the Turkish version adopted by Sahin and Heppner (1993) 35-item inventory problem solving skills are used. The data analyses in SPSS 20.00, Descriptive Statistic, T-test, One-Way Anova test and Correlation (r statistic) were used. The coaches who participated in the study TASI average $x = 1.96 \pm 0.27$, PSS average $x = 2.92 \pm 0.63$. When the time to coaching the coaches who participated in the study, 33 coaches of 1-9 years, 40 coaches of 10-19 years and 22 coaches 20 years and over. The coaches of the TASI and PSS mean scores did not change significantly compared to the working time in the profession and marital status variables, according to the education level was found to be significantly changed. The coaches between TASI and PSS average score were found to be positive and significantly correlation.

Keywords: trainer, trait anxiety, problem solving

1. Introduction

With technological and scientific development, many records have been renewed in different sport branches, and the teams and sportsmen who are encountered in the

ⁱ Correspondence: email katra10@hotmail.com

competition areas are in competition with each other in the economic field, educational field, technological and development levels of the countries they represent. The most important factor which indicates the level of development of the country is the sport (Gümüş, 2002). Nowadays, it has been mentioned that several factors affect the level of sporty performance. These factors are considered as environmental factors and internal factors. One of the internal factors of athletes is also psychological factors. Psychological preparation of athletes on the competition is an important factor for success in sport. The anxiety level of the athletes; their psychological situations are closely related to their performances (Gülşen, 2008). The concept of anxiety has become the focus by undertaking a significant role in the psychology (Hackfort ve Spielberger, 1989; Martens, Vealey, ve Burton, 1990). Anxiety can be defined as a feeling of insecurity with a mixed state of excitement and distrust in the state of waiting and breaking something about the future (Öncül 2000, Coşkun ve Akkaş, 2009) as well as being defined as a possibility of danger from environmental factors or a situation experienced in the face of an individual and perceives as a danger (Alisinanoğlu ve Ulutaş, 2003).

Trainer is a person who runs a team or an athlete, trains and makes them gain condition or coaches for the competition. Trainer is also an individual who should show leadership qualities. For leading an individual as a leader and for being a leader himself, a person is required to carry many features. Because leaders bears a lot of responsibilities as designing the work of a team, organizing their relationships and reaching the targeted success, they must have some particular qualities (Doğan, 2005).

All the features that an athlete brought because of the genetic structure may be effective in success. However, the coach is the person who will give form to genetic features of an athlete. With the guidance of trainer, the team becomes harmonious and the athlete's behavior is improved as desired. This performance is a need on the path to the success. The trainer who includes some features from technical and psychological can keep away from mistakes (Amman ve ark., 2000). One of these features is to produce an effective and accurate solution within the shortest time when faced with a problem. Ülküer (1988); problem solving is a process from feeling the difficulties that person faced in accessing a purpose to the process of thinking until find a solution and overcoming the problem. Heppner ve Krauskopf (1987) states that coping up with a problem is in the same sense of the resolution of the problem. Solving a personal problem in real life in order to ensure a number of external or internal adaptations, it is not possible to simplify problem solving as rational, cognitive and coherent information processing. The reason is that problem-solving is an active as well as being dynamic in real life. Resolving of personal problems is very complex process. A typical problem can be solved immediately or may involve many decisions. As there are many possible solutions, it may be ambiguous enough to prevent evaluation.

Anxiety refers to an unpleasant sensation. It is a permanent feeling which is characterized by anxiety and fear (Cashmore, 2002). This sense or truth which is defined as anxiety and a state of anxiety creates a tension in the absence of a significant hazard (Buckworth ve Dishman, 2002). In general, the conditions of experiencing negative feelings cause the appearance of anxiety. The symptoms of anxiety exacerbate by approaching of anxiety formed external conditions to the people who has anxiety. While anxiety is circumstantially being lived in the current conditions, symptoms of anxiety disappears with the end of the condition in which a person being forced. However, a person's inherent permanent anxiety manifests itself in the whole life by feeling more in different situations (Baltaş, 1998). Anxiety which stimulates the sympathetic nervous system accompanied by concern is a feeling that increases sweating, the heart beat and respiration. Although anxiety is a part of daily life and warns us against the potential dangers, persons who are waiting for important news, or who are in unpredictable or uncontrollable situations, become extremely sensitive about anxiety. This leads to worry and psychological tension in the general sense. In addition, those who are in dangerous or in an unfamiliar with the situation that they have previously experienced, gets completely scared. Shortly, these feelings can be adapted to each other because both of these feelings give us the power to deal with danger and threat (Tavris ve Wade, 2001).

In general, two types of anxiety are defined in sport literature. On the one hand, the state of anxiety is temporary. On the other hand, in general terms, anxiety is a stable personality trait in those who are constantly anxious. Because there is a perceptible predisposition in certain situations, anxiety is threatening and provoking. Technically the state of anxiety is subjective and the conscious perceived sensations in some environmental situations explain that there is a general tendency among people as to feel tension and anxious. (Spielberger, 1966).

State anxiety is the condition in which the individual is found and consists of the threats and causing the danger or it occurs by the result of being perceived, understood and interpreted in this way. The unpleasant, irritating emotional state is understandable, perceived and felt. Consciousness that is open in the process is alert and aware. The symptoms come to fruition in the function of the individual's plant nervous system which indicates the changes (Köknel, 2013).

High levels of trait anxiety are the result of layers that make up the personality and the function of the personality structure in our daily lives and cause the level of state anxiety to increase excessively and severely in overcoming obstacles and problem solving situations (Özgüven, 1994).

Trait anxiety is a personality trait that differs among people. Those with a high level of trait anxiety tend to be more likely than those with a low level to perceive a

stressful situation as more threat or danger and more intense tendency to react with anxiety reactions (Özgüven, 1994). The continuous anxiety scale measures anxiety according to how an individual generally and constantly feels about him or herself and measures whether or not there is a tendency to perceive, see, and interpret the situation as neutral, which is usually threatening and stressful, according to objective measures in which the person is found (Özgüven, 1994).

The anxiety scale measures anxiety according to how an individual generally and constantly feels about him or herself and measures whether or not there is a tendency to perceive,. Problem solving is a thought that is directed at solving a specific problem involving the formation of reactions and choosing the most appropriate one among the possible responses (Akt. Dinn, 2011).

Effective problem solving is a comprehensive process. The real resources of this process extend far beyond the tension-creative obstacles that temporarily interfere in a way of progression and extend to the mobilized emotions and behaviors of the problem solving individuals. It should be known that the opportunity to find a solution in a suspicious situation will give person an ability to do analysis. This truth must be understood that effective problem solving begins with encouraging self-confidence, courage and willingness as "*It is possible to solve this problem in one way or another. That's why we will find a real solution*" (Oğuzkan, 1973).

When we look at the written sources, it is seen that there are not sufficient number of studies about the referees and coaches while problem solving studies with sportsmen are available. Therefore, considering the roles and responsibilities of soccer coaches, it is expected that the investigation of the effects of trait anxiety levels on problem solving abilities will have important consequences for both researchers and practitioners.

2. Material and Method

2.1 Model of the research

Research includes descriptive and relational models. It includes a descriptive model in terms of presenting the present situation and a relational model in terms of looking at the relationship between the trait anxiety states of trainers and problem solving skills.

2.2 Population and sample

While soccer coaches working in TFF Marmara Region (Bursa and Canakkale) constitute the population of the research, the sample consists of 95 football coaches who participate voluntarily among these coaches. In order to reach the football coaches, the representatives of the Turkish Football Coaches Association (TÜFAD) located in the

province were used. However, despite this effective way, the fact that some of the coaches are not active, the active ones participating not voluntarily, or the lack of their interest and many other restrictive reasons have prevented our research from becoming more involved. There are registered teams in 5 professional 244 amateur leagues in Bursa. But 153 of the amateur teams are actively participating in the league. There are 1 professional 90 amateur teams in Canakkale but 49 of amateur teams are actively involved. The classification of coach training certificate that coaches have is as follows; TFFA=7, TFFB=25, TFFC=30, UEFA A=15, UEFA B=18.

2.3 Instruments

2.3.1 State-Trait Anxiety Inventory

The Trait Anxiety Scale developed by Beck is a 20-item scale. The scale is rated 4 of likert type. It is accepted that as you get closer to 4, trait anxiety scores increase and the opposite, as you get closer to 1, it decreases.

The scores obtained from the scale range theoretically from 20 to 80. Bigger score indicates high anxiety level; small score indicates low anxiety level. The same situation is also valid when points are interpreted according to percentile sequence. That is, the low percentile sequence (1, 5, 10) shows that anxiety is low/less. An average score level determined in practice ranges from 36 to 40.

2.3.2 Problem Solving Inventory

PCE is a likert type scale consisting of 35 items and scored among 1-6. The high total scores received from the scale indicate that an individual perceives himself as inadequate in problem-solving skills. This scale is like (1) always acting like this, (2) mostly acting like this, (3) often acting like this, (4) occasionally acting like this, (5) rarely acting like this. The answers are given points ranging from 1 to 6. Items 9, 22 and 29 are excluded from the scoring. Scoring is based on 32 items. 1, 2, 3, 4, 11, 13, 14, 15, 17, 21, 25, 26, 30 and 34 are scored inversely (akt. Bezci, 2010).

2.4 Data Analysis

Analysis of the data was performed in the SPSS. 20.00 program. While Independent Sample T-test was used in analyzing the percentages, frequency distributions as well as binary variables, One-way, Anova test was used when there were too many variables. Independent Sample T-test was used in analyzing the percentages, frequency distributions as well as binary variables. One-way, Anova test was used when there were too many variables. The Post-Hock Tuckey test was used to determine if there was any significant difference between the groups in the Anova test results. The correlation between the two variables is examined with the r-statistic.

3. Findings

95 football coaches participated voluntarily to the research. The ages of football coaches vary between 25 and 72 and the average is 46, 8. 87 of the football coaches are married, 8 are single. When the educational status of coaches is considered, it has seen that there are 8 primary school graduate, 61 high school graduate and 26 university graduates. The average of the coaches who participated in the study is $x = 1,96 \pm 0,27$ and their PCB average is $x=2,92 \pm 0,63$.

Table 1: Soccer coaches' average scores of SKO points and the state of the education variable of the PCB average scores

Educational status		n	x	SD	f	p
SKO	Primary Education	8	2,02	0,28	3.03	0.05*
	High School	61	1,87	0,26		
	University	26	1,78	0,21		
	Total	95	1,86	0,26		
PCB	Primary Education	8	3,20	0,34	2.64	0.77
	High School	61	2,92	0,68		
	University	26	2,65	0,63		
	Total	95	2,87	0,66		

P<0.05

Table 2: T-test result showing soccer coaches' average scores of SKO points and the state of the marital status variable of the PCB average scores

Marital Status		N	X	SS	t	p
PBC	Single	8	2,58	0,46	-1.76	0.20
	Married	86	2,89	0,67		
SKO	Single	8	1,75	0,21	-1.43	0.18
	Married	86	1,87	0,26		

Table 3: The relation between football coaches' SKO and PCB

		Age	SKO	PCBO
SKO	r	0,32**	1	0,27**
	p	0,00		0,00
	N	95	95	95
PCB	r	0,20*	0,27**	1
	p	0,04	0,00	
	N	95	95	95

According to Table 3, it is observed that the SKO scores of the football coaches are positively correlated with the age variable of 0.32 (32%). It is observed that PCA levels have a positive correlation at 0.20 (20%) level. It is interpreted as the score of problem skills decreases, the level of problem skills of the individual increases and the problem skill score increases, the level of the problem skill of the individual decreases.

4. Conclusion

This research work aimed at examining the relation between problem solving skills of football coaches and their scores in trait anxiety. Through the content of this work, the level of relation between two variable factors alongside with the relation between the average scores of PÇB and SKÖ and demographic factors has also been examined. It was recorded in table 1 that, meaning wise, any change has not been observed on the average PÇB score of the coaches who participated in this research, according to the educational factor. ($p > 0.05$). İşmen (2001), Karaca and ark (2013) in their titled work: "*the relation between teachers' problem solving skills before school and their self respect*" stated that: no change has been seen in the problem solving skills of teachers before and after school. Again, it was seen in table 1 that, the average SKO score of the coaches who participated in this research, according to the educational factor has some changes meaning wise ($p > 0.05$). Average SKO score of coaches with basic educational background has been seen to be higher than that of coaches with high school and university educational background. The rise in the total score collected from the scale of PCB inventory can lead to the saying that: with the perception of inadequacy of individual problem solving skills, the coaches' problem solving skills rises whenever their education is advanced.

Table 2 stated that, according to the marital status of the coaches, their SKO and PCB scores has not changed as far as meaning is concerned ($p > 0.05$). Pamuk, Hamurcu and Armağan(2014) in their research with candidates for class teaching, Kutanis and Tunç (2013) Hemşireler Kaya and Varol (2004), in their works proved that trait anxiety according to marital status factor, did not change as far as the meaning is concerned. Kelleci and Gölbaşı (2004) in their titled work: "*Observation on nurses working in a university hospital from the perspective of some factors*", did not find any significant statistical difference between their problem solving skills and their marital status. Demirtaş and Dönmez (2008) in their work to assess the perception of teachers in secondary school about their problem solving skills, did not record any difference between their perceptions based on marital status factor. Aside this, there are some written references that show differences in problem solving skills according to the marital status factor.

Pehlivan and Konukman (2004) in their titled work: "*A comparative work between physical education teachers and other teachers on the bases of problem solving skills*" concluded that, the level of problem solving skills of married ones was higher than that of those who were not married. Kaya (2005) in her dissertation, titled: "*Problem solving skills of nurses and enlightenment on some effective factors*" found out that – even though not meaning wise- the problem solving skills of married nurses was higher.

Table 3 clearly shows that, the SKÖ scores of the football coaches have positively correlated with the age factor on the level of 0.32(%32). Engür (2002) Yücel (2003), Erbaş (2005), have arrived in their various works at a result showing how effective the age factor is on trait anxiety. However, Türkçapar (2012), Aktaş (2009), Develi (2006), Ekşi (2006), Tekkoyun (2008) in their works did not come across -meaning wise- any relation between the age factor and trait anxiety. A look at the literature reveals that, findings on relation between the age factor and trait anxiety score always differ. While the researches taken out on sportsmen shows the positive or negative effects of age factor on trait anxiety, the ones taken on teachers and coaches did not show any relation between the age factor and trait anxiety as far as the meaning is concerned. It can also be seen that the PCB levels too have a positive correlation with the age factor on the level of 0.20(%20). Thus, it is right to say, the football coaches' problem solving skills decreases whenever there is a rise in their ages. But it is not right to say, when a person's problem solving skills score decreases, his problem solving skills rises and vice-versa. Aside this, it is also seen that the levels of SOK and PCK correlated positively on the level of 0.27(%27). Based on this result, whenever there is a rise in the coaches' trait anxiety scores, their problem solving skills levels show a drop off. However, it is wrong to say when there is a drop off in problem solving skills scores, there is definitely a rise in problem solving skills, it is also wrong to say when there is a rise in problem solving scores, there is automatically a fall in trait anxiety levels. Taylan (1990), in his research, proved that there is a positive relation between trait anxiety and problem solving scores meaning wise. He put forth in his work that, when there is a rise in trait anxiety scores, there is also a rise in problem solving scores. Çam and Tümkaya (2008), have also proven a positive and meaningful relation between problem solving skills between individuals and trait anxiety. Hamarta (2009), too has proven a meaningful relation between adolescents' problem solving skills and their social anxieties. Karataş (2011) also proved in his work, the positive but meaningful relation between problem solving skills and trait anxiety. All these works show almost the same thing in line with the findings of this research.

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